

Analytical techniques for the preconcentration and separation of mononitrophenols[†]

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Abstract : Nitroaromatic compounds form an important class of industrial chemicals with substantial marketing volumes. The toxicity of nitroaromatics to aquatic organisms has been investigated for more than 25 years. Analytical methods for control of quality of waters are required to be highly specific and possibly highly sensitive for the determination of even low amounts of pollutants. The main problems encountered during the analysis are the separation of matrix components from the pollutants of interest and the achievement of low detection limits. Therefore, an overview on different materials and techniques available for sample concentration and/or matrix removal will be provided and discussed according to the chemical characteristics of the pollutant that has to be enriched. The aim of this review is to provide a general overview on the analytical methods proposed in the last decade for trace mononitrophenols determination in environmental waters.

Keywords : Phenols, mononitrophenols, preconcentration, nanoparticles, nanomaterials, GC-MS, HPLC-MS, MWCNTs, EPA, *o*-NP, PNP, *m*-NP.

Introduction

Phenolic compounds are present in the environment as a result of their uses and the processes in which they are implicated. Although they can be originated naturally due to the degradation of humic substances, tannins and lignins, many industrial processes, including production of drugs, textiles, dyes, pesticides and paper, are the main source of these compounds in the environment.

Phenols due to their toxicity, persistence and common occurrence in the biosphere are one of the most important group of ecotoxins. These compounds are in a common use such as ingredients (components) and precursors of other chemicals including organic polymers, solvents, dyes (aminophenols), explosives (nitrophenols), surfactants (alkylphenols) or drugs. The occurrence of phenols in the environment is also related to production and degradation of many pesticides, e.g. phenoxyherbicides like 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic, dinoseb acid or phenolic biocides such as 4-chlorophenol or pentachlorophenol, parathion¹⁻⁴.

Nitrophenols which fall under substituted phenols are important and versatile organic compounds in industrial,

agricultural and defence applications. They are frequently used as intermediates in the manufacture of explosives, pharmaceuticals, pesticides, pigments, dyes, rubber chemicals, lumber preservatives, photographic chemicals, to mention a few. They are also produced by microbial hydrolysis of several organo-phosphorus pesticides, for example parathion, or by photodegradation of pesticides that contain the nitrophenol moiety. *o*-Nitrophenol (*o*-NP), in particular, poses significant health risks since it is toxic to mammals, microorganisms and anaerobic bacteria. Its toxicity is thought to be due to the nitro group being easily reduced by enzymes to the nitro anion radical, nitroso and hydroxylamine derivatives. These derivatives are responsible for the cytotoxic, mutagenic and carcinogenic properties of nitro compounds^{5,6}. The detection and analysis of nitrophenols in both waste and potable water is thus important.

p-Nitrophenol is a potential environmental contaminant of water due to its high solubility into water. It readily breaks down in surface water but persists longer in deep soil and in groundwater and due to its toxicity causes deadly effects on the ecosystem. PNP irritates the eyes,

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

skin, and respiratory tract. It may also cause inflammation of those parts. Acute exposure of PNP may lead to liver and kidney damage, anaemia, skin and eye irritation, and systemic poisoning. The US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has listed *p*-nitrophenol (PNP) as a priority pollutant and recommended its concentrations in natural waters and drinking waters to below 10 ng/L whereas, monthly average industrial effluent concentrations of PNP should not exceed 162 µg/L. The major sources of wastes that discharge PNP are the industries mainly involved in the management of explosives, drugs, dyes, phosphoorganic insecticides (methyl parathion), pesticides and leather.

The main input of PNP into the environment is the hydrolysis of methyl parathion or parathion, which are commonly used as pesticides in agriculture. PNP is also found in industrial wastes since it is a precursor not only of pesticides such as carbofuran, nitrofen, methyl parathion and parathion, but also of certain pharmaceuticals, plasticizers, azo dyes, explosives etc. In addition, diesel fuel and gasoline exhaust also contain PNP. Because of the widespread nature of *p*-nitrophenol and other nitrophenols, they are considered as major pollutants by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA)⁷.

The purpose of this review is to provide a condensed summary of methods that are both advanced and rapid. The term 'rapid' can have different meanings depending upon the perspective and expectations of the analyst and the context of the analytical environment. Analysts should exercise caution when evaluating descriptions of rapid methods. In this paper a review of the analytical methods and techniques for determination of mononitrophenols is presented. The methods and techniques were divided into four groups : chromatographic, electrochemical, and capillary electrophoretic and miscellaneous methods.

Analytical methods and techniques

The review of the papers showed that analytical techniques have been applied for determination of mononitrophenols, such as chromatography, voltammetry, electrochemical, capillary electrophoresis and other methods.

Chromatographic methods

Chromatographic techniques belong to the most often employed group of analytical methods for identification and determination of nitrophenols in biological material. Chromatography is the general term for various separatory methods, all of which have in common the distribution of

a component between a mobile phase (a liquid or gas) and a stationary phase (a solid or liquid). The analyte is injected into a mobile phase (liquid for HPLC or gas for gas chromatography), which is then forced under pressure through a column⁸.

Chromatography can be divided into two categories, namely, gas and liquid chromatography. Gas chromatography (GC) is used for the analysis of volatile samples, and liquid chromatography (LC) for non-volatile samples with a molecular weight smaller than 2000. Many samples simply cannot be handled by GC. Either they are insufficiently volatile and cannot pass through the column, or they are thermally unstable and decompose under the conditions of separation. It has been estimated that only 20% of known organic compounds can be satisfactorily separated by GC, without prior chemical modification of the sample. On the other hand, LC is not limited by sample volatility or thermal stability. LC in chromatographic methods is a separation method of great importance to the chemical, pharmaceutical and biotechnological industries. The principle is that a sample of a solution of the substances is injected into a column of a porous material (stationary phase) and a liquid (mobile phase) is pumped through the column. The separation of substances is based on differences in rates of migration through the column arising from different partition of the substances between the stationary and the mobile phase. LC technique became a rapidly powerful separation technique and is today called high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The development of HPLC opened a new era in bio-related fields and allowed faster separations of fragile macromolecules. Reversed-phase liquid chromatography (RPLC) is the most popular mode of chromatography for the analytical and preparative separations of compounds of interest in the chemical, biological, pharmaceutical and biomedical sciences. In reversed-phase gradient HPLC, the mobile phase changes composition over a specified time. A steady increase in the percentage of organic solvent (acetonitrile, methanol, propanol) leads to an increase in the mobile phase elutropic strength and this makes it possible for highly retained non-polar analyte to be analyzed within the same run as poorly retained polar analytes⁹.

For rapid analysis HPLC, it is important to decrease column length, increase flow rate, and use fast gradient elution. Current HPLC column technology is focused on the use of smaller particles (<2 µm). The increased efficiency of these particles will give a sufficient increase in resolution so that columns can be shortened and flow

rates increased. Common detectors used for HPLC are UV absorbance, refractive index detectors, fluorescence detectors, electrochemical detectors (including amperometric and conductivity), radioactivity detectors, and a variety of light-scattering detectors including multi-angle laser light scattering and evaporative light scattering. More recently, mass spectrometry (MS) has been introduced as a highly sensitive and specific detector for HPLC analyzes. During the past 10 years several approaches have tried to interface LC to MS, including thermospray particle beam and electrospray (ES) interfaces. Recently, the most important detection used in biopharmaceutical analysis is MS with the electrospray ionization (ESI) and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) techniques¹⁰.

HPLC analysis of *p*-nitrophenol was determined by the Kulkarni *et al.* by using the *P. putida* from various samples¹¹. Galeano *et al.* made a rapid, sensitive liquid chromatography combined with electrochemical method for the determination of nitrophenol from parathion, nitropesticides and 3-methyl-4-nitrophenol from river water as well as fortified water samples¹².

A new fluorescent labelling reagent, 2-(9-carbazole)-ethyl chloroformate (CEOC) for the determination of phenol, *p*-chlorophenol, 2,5-dimethylphenol, 2,4-dichlorophenol and 1,4-dihydroxybenzene from printing ink by Zhang *et al.* Hollow fiber membrane was used to preconcentrate nitrophenols and determined by capillary liquid chromatography from sea water¹³.

Determination of parathion metabolite, *p*-nitrophenol in urine of parathion factory workers by Han *et al.* from urine samples¹⁴. LC determination of mono-substituted phenols in water using liquid-liquid-liquid phase microextraction by Yazadi *et al.* and the method was applied to the determination of phenols in tap and well waters¹⁵. Penalver *et al.* determine the phenolic compounds from various water samples¹⁶. Ye *et al.* determine the phenols from urine samples using HPLC-MS/MS method¹⁷.

Determination of phenolic compounds from environmental samples from Spain were studied by Martinez *et al.* Liquid phase microextraction of phenols were determined from water samples¹⁸.

Zhao *et al.* determined the phenols from water samples using the liquid chromatography¹⁹.

Polyaniline-coated Pt-fiber were used for the preconcentration of volatile phenols in water by Mousavi *et al.* Multi-walled carbon nanotubes bonded fused-silica

fiber were used for the solid phase microextraction of phenols in water samples²⁰⁻²².

Electrochemical methods

This modality utilizes the electrolysis laws in which cationic species are deposited on electrodes surfaces, when an electrolyte cell composed by three electrodes (reference, work, auxiliary) is used, it is possible to attainable selective separation and preconcentration of analyte. Electrochemical methods have proven to be useful for the development of very sensitive and selective methods for the determination of organic molecules; including drugs. Addition application of electroanalytical techniques includes the determination of electrode mechanisms. Redox properties of pollutants can give insights into its metabolic fate or their biological system redox processes. Most electrochemical techniques, especially voltammetry and polarography but also those of electrochemical stripping, have extremely good sensitivities and detection limits. They could determine electroactive species at 10^{-3} – 10^{-11} mol L⁻¹ concentration levels. Most electrochemical techniques, especially voltammetry and polarography but also those of electrochemical stripping, have extremely good sensitivities and detection limits. They could determine electroactive species at 10^{-3} – 10^{-11} mol L⁻¹ concentration levels. The electrochemical determination of *p*-nitrophenol and its derivatives using multiple pulsed amperometry with graphite based electrodes by Basela *et al.* This modality utilizes the electrolysis laws in which cationic species are deposited on the electrodes surface. When an electrolytic cell composed by three electrodes (reference, work and auxiliary) is used, it is possible to attained selective separation and preconcentration of nitrophenols. A poly(methylene blue)-modified glassy carbon electrode had been used for determination of 4-nitrophenol in real water samples²³.

Multi-walled carbon nanotube-poly(diphenylamine) (MWCNT-PDPA) composite film modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE) and its application for the electrochemical reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) by Yang *et al.* from real sample analysis²⁴. A graphene modified and MWNT electrode used for the electrochemical oxidation of *p*-nitrophenol and determined by cyclic and differential pulse voltammetry by Arvinte *et al.* and El-Mhammedi *et al.* Studied the behaviour of apatite-modified carbon paste electrode for the preconcentration of *p*-nitrophenol from river and determined by cyclic and square wave voltammetry. Cathodic electrochemical detection of 4-nitrophenol by bismuth film electrode (BiFE) determined by amperometry by Hutton *et al.*²⁵.

Sodium montmorillonite-anthraquinone chemically modified glassy carbon electrode from water samples by Hu *et al.* and determined by cyclic voltammetrically²⁶. Luo *et al.* determine the nitrophenols using the carbon nanotubes modified electrode by derivative voltammetry²⁷.

The sensor was prepared by modifying the electrode with lithium tetracyanoethylenide (LiTCNE) and poly-L-lysine (PLL) film²⁸. Poly(methylene blue)-modified glass electrode had been applied for the determination of *p*-nitrophenols in nanomolar by Giribabu *et al.*²⁹. Modified carbon electrode modified with crown ether/silver nanoparticles had been applied for the voltammetric studies of *p*-nitrophenol³⁰.

Capillary electrophoretic methods

CE, also known as capillary zone electrophoresis (CZE), can be used to separate ionic species by their charge and frictional forces. CE is a simple analysis technique which is applied to the separation of a wide variety of compound types, including pharmaceuticals. In this area two separation modes of CE, CZE and micellar electrokinetic capillary chromatography (MECC), are mostly used. Capillary electrophoresis (CE) is an important separation technique. In CE, the migration of any charged species depends primarily on the charge-to-mass ratio and, to a certain extent on the shape, size and conformation (for large molecules). When the analytes have similar charge-to-mass ratios and other parameters are very close, CE can become an inadequate technique for their separation. However, the identification of a given species in a mixture is often of importance, such as in the case when there are no authentic standards available. Therefore, other means are required to confirm the presence or absence of a specific species.

Wei *et al.* pH-mediated dual-cloud point extraction (d-CPE) technique for capillary electrophoresis (CE) determination of phenol and *m*-nitrophenol from spiked natural water samples³¹. Separation conditions are optimized by Rudolph *et al.*³² for the preconcentration of *p*-nitrophenol and organic acids in atmospheric aerosols. A three-phase hollow fiber liquid-phase microextraction method coupled with CE was developed and used for the determination of partition coefficients and analysis of selected nitrophenols (2-nitrophenol, 3-nitrophenol, 4-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol and 2,6-dinitrophenol) in water samples. The developed method was successfully applied for the analysis of water samples³³. *o*-Nitrophenol, *m*-nitrophenol, and *p*-nitrophenol could well be separated by capillary zone electrophoresis (CZE)

by Guo *et al.*; it can be developed for the separation of practical samples in environment analysis and the separation and determination of nitrophenol isomers by high-performance capillary zone electrophoresis in environment analysis³⁴.

Miscellaneous methods

Different techniques have tried to offer new options for screening nitrophenols. Screening consists on rapid and/or *in situ* detection. There are two main difficulties for an effective screening method: the necessity of a very high sensitivity, which in fact is a necessity of any technique; and the demand of preliminary sample preparations. Some of these techniques, which are commented ahead, present a lack of applications because of their practical inconveniences or because they have not been proved yet with real samples.

Silica magnetite nanoparticles mixed hemimicelle sorbents had been used for the extraction of phenolic compounds from environmental water samples by Zhao *et al.*³⁵. Carbon nanotube/ionic liquid/chitosan composite film modified electrode for the determination of *p*-nitrophenol from lake water by Chen *et al.* A macroporous imprinted polymer containing gold nanoparticles were used for the electrochemical detection of *p*-nitrophenol by Xu *et al.* A multi-walled carbon nanotube Nafion-modified electrode had been used for the simultaneous determination of *o*-nitrophenol and *p*-nitrophenol from lake water samples by Huang *et al.* A electrochemical method of 4-nitrophenol using single wall carbon nanotube film glassy carbon electrode had been employed to determine 4-nitrophenol in lake water samples. Adsorption of *o*-nitrophenol on multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNTs) and carboxylic group functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes had been developed by Arasteh *et al.* from water as well as waste water samples³⁶. Polypyrrole-coated magnetic nanoparticles based on anion exchange process for the extraction of mononitrophenols from various water samples by Tahmasebi *et al.* Removal of *p*-nitrophenol and naphthalene from petrochemical wastewater using SWCNTs and SWCNT-COOH surfaces by Moradi *et al.* Electrochemical detection of 4-nitrophenol based on a glassy carbon electrode modified with a reduced grapheme oxide/Au nanoparticles composite by Tang *et al.*³⁷⁻⁴². Preparation of silica-magnetite nanoparticle mixed hemimicelle sorbents for extraction of several typical phenolic compounds from environmental water samples. Multi-walled carbon nano-tube/ionic liquid/chitosan composite film modified electrode had been applied for the

determination of *p*-nitrophenol from lake water. Nanoporous gold based electrochemical sensor had been applied for the detection of *p*-nitrophenol. Carbon nanotube modified electrode had been applied for the detection of mononitrophenols by Luo *et al.*⁴³. Macroporous imprinted polymer containing gold nanoparticles had been applied by Guilin *et al.*⁴⁴ for the selective recognition and electrochemical detection of *p*-nitrophenol. Cyclodextrin-coated quantum dots had been applied for detection of phenols from various water samples by Haibing *et al.*⁴⁵. Mixed hemimicelles based on cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) coated nanomagnets Fe₃O₄ was investigated for the preconcentration of chlorophenols in environmental water samples prior to HPLC-spectrophotometry⁴⁶.

Spectrophotometric methods are simple and rapid so these methods can be successfully used for pharmaceutical analysis. These methods are mostly based on the formation of colored complexes between drug and the reagent which can be determined by visible spectrophotometry. UV, derivative, photometry, fluorimetry spectrophotometric methods have been used for mononitrophenols. A new spectrophotometric method was developed for the simultaneous of ternary mixtures of nitrophenol isomers, without prior separation steps. This method is called the first derivative of the density ratio spectra developed by Bagheban-Shahri *et al.* had developed a sensitive method for the spectrophotometric determination of nitrophenols from various environmental samples. In synthetic and natural water samples⁴⁷, a first derivative spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of parathion and *p*-nitrophenol in vegetable tissues as well as corn leaf by Toral *et al.*⁴⁸. Spectrophotometric determination of trace *p*-nitrophenol enriched by 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid-modified nanometer TiO₂ in water in industrial wastewaters and natural waters. 2-[(*E*)-2-(4-Diethylaminophenyl)-1-ethenyl]-1,3,3-trimethyl-3*H*-indolium as a new highly sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of nitrophenols by Shkumbatiuk *et al.*⁴⁹ and Akarami *et al.* Simultaneous determination of nitrophenol isomers in environmental samples using first derivation of density ratio spectra⁵⁰.

Conclusions

Developing green and sustainable technology for the effluent treatment is very important research area in this era of industrial and social development. Many researchers have carried out the research in this field. One of the important pollutants from this point of view is phenol. It

has its presence in the effluent from major chemical and pharmaceutical industries such as petrochemical industries, petroleum refineries, coal gasification operations, liquefaction process, resin manufacturing industries, dye synthesis units, pulp and paper mills and pharmaceutical industries. It is a highly corrosive and nerve poisoning agent. Phenol causes harmful side effects such as sour mouth, diarrhoea, impaired vision, excretion of dark urine. It is also toxic for fishes. The occurrence of emerging contaminants in the aquatic environment is of increasing interest, as modern sensitive techniques are employed worldwide for their determination. This review covers the current status and future prospects about the application of modern analytical instruments (such as GC-MS or LC-MS) for the analysis of emerging contaminants in aquatic system, in the past years. A large number of studies have been developed on this topic in reason of the importance of their monitoring in the studies of environmental mobility and potential degradation pathways. To conclude, various methods showing good reliability, accuracy and sensitivity are currently available, and they represent monitoring tools to get information on the occurrence, behaviour and fate of such compounds into the aquatic environment, giving a precious contribute to the understanding of their lifecycle after use.

Abbreviations

SPE : Solid phase extraction, HPLC : High performance liquid chromatography, GC : Gas chromatography, CP : Capillary electrophoresis, EC : Electrochemical, RP-HPLC : Reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography, DNP : Dinitrophenol, MWCNTs : Multi-walled carbon nanotubes, EPA : Environmental protection agency, ESI : Electrospray ionization, PNP : *p*-Nitrophenol, *o*-NP : *o*-Nitrophenol, APCI : Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization techniques, MECC : Micellar electrokinetic capillary chromatography, LOD—limit of detection, LOQ—limit of quantitation.

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